

Clinico-Etiological Profile of Neonates with Jaundice in a Tertiary Care Hospital of North Coastal Andhra PradeshP.V.S.S. Vijaya Babu¹, K.V. Phani Madhavi², V. Soumya³, K. Pradyumna⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram, Andhra Pradesh³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam⁴Medical Officer, Suraksha Hospital, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:**Background:** The most common cause of delayed discharges and readmissions from hospitals during the first week of life is neonatal jaundice. Early detection of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia is crucial to preventing serious complications. The aim of this study was to investigate the clinical profile and etiology of neonatal jaundice.**Methods:** This prospective observational study was conducted in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU), Department of Paediatrics, Government Medical College, Srikakulam, over a period of 1 Year (August 2022 to July 2023). A total of 100 cases were enrolled for the study. Data collection was done by history taking, clinical examination and relevant laboratory investigations.**Results:** In this study, out of 100 jaundiced neonates, 65% were males and 35% were females, 82 % were born at term and remaining 18% were preterm babies. Among 100 neonates studied, majority (83%) had birth weight ≥ 2500 gm. Only 17 % had birth weight less than 2500 gm. Physiological jaundice was seen in 54% of the total cases. This was followed by ABO incompatibility (18%), Rh incompatibility (13%), sepsis (2%), idiopathic (1%), prematurity (6%), cephalhematoma (4%) and breastfeeding jaundice (2%).**Conclusions:** This study concludes that physiological jaundice is the most common cause of neonatal jaundice in our hospital. This was followed by ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility and sepsis. This highlights the importance of appropriate monitoring of neonates with these underlying risk factors.**Keywords:** ABO incompatibility, Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, Physiological jaundice, Rh incompatibility.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Neonatal jaundice, also known as neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, is a common condition in newborns where the skin, eyes, and mucous membranes turn yellow due to excess bilirubin in the blood. According to the American Academy of Paediatrics, it's defined as a total serum bilirubin level greater than 5 mg/dL. [1]

It's estimated that: 60% of full-term infants will develop jaundice in the first week, 80% of preterm infants will develop jaundice in the first week. [2] Neonatal jaundice is usually harmless and self-limiting, but can be a sign of an underlying condition that requires medical attention if accompanied by symptoms such as excessive vomiting, fever, or changes in behaviour. Jaundice is indeed a common reason for delayed hospital discharge and readmissions in the first week of life. In fact, it's estimated that jaundice is the leading cause of delayed hospital discharge and

readmissions in the first week of life. [3,4] Premature babies, or preterm babies, have a higher rate of bilirubin production compared to full-term babies. This is because their red blood cells have a shorter lifespan and a higher turnover rate. [5] Multifactorial causes can lead to neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. It could be disease-related or physiological. Neonates can develop physiological hyperbilirubinemia for a variety of reasons. [6,7]

Babies, particularly those born before their due date, produce more bilirubin because they have more red blood cells and are more susceptible to haemolysis. Additionally, because of a decrease in gastrointestinal tract motility in the first few days of life, newborns have enhanced enterohepatic circulation, which results in bilirubin reabsorption. Neonates also experience physiological volume restriction as a result of the low amounts of breast milk. Delay in cutting the cord might also be a risk

factor. Asphyxia, sepsis, rhesus incompatibility, exposure to haemolytic drugs, and ABO incompatibility are a few pathogenic reasons of hyperbilirubinemia in neonates. In over 50% of instances, the cause of newborn hyperbilirubinemia may not be fully understood. [8]

Even while only 5–10% of newborns with pathological hyperbilirubinemia require treatment, there is always a danger of brain impairment, especially when the bilirubin level is extremely high, there are risk factors present, or the care is inadequate. [9, 10] Severe newborn jaundice may result in bilirubin encephalopathy, which may then have long-term, irreversible neurologic consequences. The survivors have significant neurological disabilities, including deafness, vision palsies, and cerebral palsy. [3,4]

Although sequela cannot be reversed, it can be avoided with prompt diagnosis and effective care for newborn jaundice. For the treatment of newborn jaundice, etiological and risk factor identification is crucial. There are regional and ethnic variations in the incidence, aetiology, and contributing factors of newborn jaundice. [11]

These parameters may differ from those in wealthy countries due to racial, cultural, and environmental differences in developing countries. The necessity for more thorough epidemiological investigations in low- and middle-income studies was emphasised in order to find additional risk variables that might be particularly relevant. [12]

Present study was undertaken to study the clinical profile and etiological factors leading to neonatal jaundice at our tertiary care centre.

Methods

This prospective, observational study was conducted in the NICU, department of paediatrics, Government Medical College, Srikakulam. The study was conducted over a period of 12 months (August 2022 to July 2023). A total of 100 cases were enrolled for the study through purposive sampling method. Institutional ethical committee approval and permission from respective authorities was obtained for conducting the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

Neonates with jaundice admitted in NICU or neonatology ward during study period, with serum bilirubin more than 10 mg/dL were included.

Exclusion criteria

Neonates with jaundice not admitted in NICU, attending outpatient department only, neonates with jaundice opted discharge against medical advice and parents not willing to participate in this study were excluded.

The purpose of the present study was explained to parents and a written consent was taken for participation. Detailed history was taken for all babies along with maternal, antenatal and delivery details. Thorough physical examination was done and the relevant investigations were carried out. General data including age, birth weight, age at detection of jaundice, breast feeding status, family history of jaundice was noted. Jaundice was ascertained by clinical methods.

This was confirmed with the help of biochemical tests. Serum bilirubin was estimated by Van den Bergh method. Further investigations were not carried out on those babies who were having physiological jaundice. Blood grouping and Rh typing of baby and mother were done.

Cord blood bilirubin and haemoglobin, direct Coomb's test (DCT) and bilirubin monitoring were done whenever there was a setting for Rh incompatibility. In case of ABO incompatibility, DCT was done and bilirubin monitored.

Other investigations like haemoglobin level, peripheral smear and reticulocyte count were done when indicated. If these tests showed features of haemolysis and there was no blood group incompatibility, G6PD assay, sickling test, haemoglobin electrophoresis and osmotic fragility test were done wherever appropriate. G6PD was done by fluorescent technique, 2% sodium metabisulphite was used for sickling test.

Osmotic fragility test using serial dilutions of sodium chloride was done. Neonates who were suspected to have sepsis were investigated by complete blood count, septic screen and blood and urine cultures. Results were expressed as percentages and ratios.

Results

There was no comparative group in this study. During study period, 100 newborns were considered for present study, as they were satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Figure 1: Gender wise distribution of neonates with Jaundice

Out of 100 jaundiced neonates, 65 (65%) were males and 35 (35%) were females as depicted in Figure 1. Among 100 newborns studied, 82 (82%) was born at term gestation and the remaining 18 (18%) were preterm babies as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Distribution of Jaundiced neonates according to gestational age, (n=100)

Table 1: Distribution of jaundiced neonates according to birth weight, (n=100).

Birth Weight	No (%)
>2500 gms	83 (83%)
<2500 gms	17(17%)
Total	100(100%)

Table 1 shows that out of 100 newborns included in this study, majority of the babies had birth weight \geq 2500 gm (83%). Only 40 babies had birth weight <2500 gm (17%).

Table 2: Etiology of neonatal jaundice, (n=100)

Etiology	No (%)
Physiological jaundice	54 (54%)
ABO incompatibility	18(18%)
Rh incompatibility	13(13%)
Sepsis	2(2%)
Idiopathic	1(1%)
Prematurity	6(6%)
Cephalhematoma	4(4%)
Breastfeeding jaundice	2 (2%)

Table 2 shows that Physiological jaundice was seen in 54% of the total cases. This was followed by ABO incompatibility (18%), Rh incompatibility (13%), sepsis (2%), idiopathic (1%), prematurity (6%), cephalhematoma (4%) and breastfeeding jaundice (2%).

Discussion

Neonatal jaundice is one of the most common causes of hospitalization of neonates in the first month after birth. In most cases, neonatal jaundice is transient and usually resolving at the end of the first week after birth. But when severe hyperbilirubinemia is present, there is a potential risk for acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus.

This can lead to death in the first months, and infants who are still alive often suffer from mental retardation, movement and balance disorders, seizures, hearing loss at high frequencies, and speech impairment. So, timely diagnosis and treatment of neonatal jaundice are very important to prevent further complications.

In this study, out of the total 100 neonates with jaundice, 65% were males and only 35% were females. Similar findings were reported from studies done by Effiong et al, Narang et al and Korejo et al where majority of the babies were males. [13-15] Majority of the babies studied were of term gestation. Only 18% were born preterm. A higher percentage of premature babies was found in studies done by Bhutani et al and Singhal et al. [16,17] In the present study, majority of the babies had birth weight ≥ 2500 gm. Only 17% of the babies had birth weight less than 2500 gm.

As our study had 82% term babies, majority (83%) had normal birth weight. In this study, physiological jaundice was found to be the major etiological factor i.e., 54 out of the total 100 babies (54%). This is in concordance to the study done by Bahl et al, wherein the physiological jaundice was observed in majority of the patients (63.8%). [18] Studies done by Singhal et al and Merchant et al observed physiological jaundice in 16.7% and 25.3% of the total cases respectively. [17,19] This was followed by ABO incompatibility as the second leading cause of neonatal jaundice in our

study (18%). This is in concordance to the studies done by Verma et al and Merchant et al, wherein ABO incompatibility contributed to 22.6% of the cases. [19,20]

After ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility was found to be responsible for 13% of the total cases. Bajpai PC et al reported an incidence of 1.6% for Rh incompatibility while Verma et al observed Rh incompatibility in 9.8% of the total cases. Thus, ABO incompatibility was more prevalent than Rh incompatibility. This is in concordance with older studies done abroad. [21,22] Similar findings were reported from India too. [17,19,20]

In this study, sepsis constituted 2% of the total cases studied. Sepsis was found to be the cause of neonatal jaundice in 8% of neonates by Merchant et al, 11.6% by Verma et al and in 9.6% of neonates by Narang et al. [19,20,14] No known cause could be established in 1% of the total cases. Studies done by Singal et al and Bahl et al observed that idiopathic jaundice was present in 8.8% to 57% of the total cases. [17,18] Prematurity as a cause of neonatal jaundice was found in 6% of the total cases. Cephalhematoma was 4% of the cases with neonatal jaundice. This is comparable to the study done by Narang et al which found that cephalhematoma was responsible for 6.3% of the total cases with neonatal jaundice. [14] There were 2 (2%) cases of breastfeeding jaundice which regressed after improving the frequency of breastfeeding.

Limitations

It is well known that there may be marked geographic variations in the pattern of etiological factors in neonatal jaundice. Therefore, our findings may not be reflective of the pattern in other regions.

Another drawback was that some etiological factors leading to neonatal jaundice like Gilbert syndrome and Crigler-Najar syndrome were not investigated. Hence there is a possibility that some of the cases classified as idiopathic may have this underlying diagnosis.

Conclusion

This study concludes that physiological jaundice is the most common cause of neonatal jaundice in our hospital. This is followed by ABO incompatibility, sepsis, Rh incompatibility and idiopathic cases. Less common causes are cephalhematoma, breast feeding jaundice and haemolytic anaemia. Understanding the aetiological and risk factors for neonatal jaundice in our setting helps in prioritizing the group of neonates who require more intensive monitoring for early identification and timely management of this condition.

References

1. Stevenson DK, Madan A. Jaundice in newborn. In: Rudolph CD, Rudolph AM, Hostetter MK, Lister G, Siegel NJ, editors. *Rudolph's pediatric*. 23rd ed, McGraw Hill. 2018.
2. Barbara JS, Kliegman RM. Jaundice and hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn. In: Kliegman RM, Behrman HB, Jenson HB, editors. *Nelson textbook of paediatrics*, 17th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders. 2004; 592-8.
3. Bhutani VK, Zipursky A, Blencowe H, Khanna R, Sgro M, Ebbesen F, et al. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia and Rhesus disease of the newborn: incidence and impairment estimates for 2010 at regional and global levels. *Pediatr Res*. 2013; 74(1):86-100.
4. Mwaniki MK, Atieno M, Lawn JE, Newton CRJC. Long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes after intrauterine and neonatal insults: A Systematic review. *Lancet*. 2012; 379 (9814):445-52.
5. Brouillard R. Measurement red blood cell lifespan. *J AM Med Assoc*. 1974; 230(9):1304-5.
6. Maisels MJ, Watchko JF, Bhutani VK, Stevenson DK. An approach to the management of hyperbilirubinemia in the preterm infant less than 35 weeks of gestation. *J Perinatol*. 2012; 32(9):660-4.
7. Stokowski, Laura A. Fundamentals of phototherapy for neonatal jaundice. *Adv Neonatal Care*. 2011; 11(5):S10-21.
8. Narang A, Kumar P, Kumar R. Neonatal jaundice in very low birth weight babies. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2001; 68:307-309.
9. Mishra S, Agarwal R, Deorari AK, Paul VK. Jaundice in the newborns. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2008; 75(2):157-63.
10. Maisels MJ, Bhutani VK, Bogen D, Newman TB, Stark AR, Watchko JF. Hyperbilirubinemia in the newborn infants >35 weeks gestation: an update with clarifications. *Pediatrics*. 2009; 124(4):1193-8.
11. Ipek IO, Bozayakut A. Clinically significant neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: an analysis of 546 cases in Istanbul. *J Trop Pediatr*. 2008; 54(3):212-3.
12. Olusanya BO, Osibanjo FB, Slusher TM. Risk factors for severe neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in low and middle-income countries: a systematic review and Meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 2015; 10(2):e0117229.
13. Effiong CE. Neonatal jaundice in Ibadan. Incidence and etiologic factors born in hospital, Nigeria. *J National Med Asso*. 1975; 67(3):208-10.
14. Narang A, Ghatwala G, Kumar P. Neonatal jaundice, an analysis of 551 cases. *Indian Paediatr*. 1996; 34:429-32.
15. Korejo H. Risk factors for kernicterus in neonatal jaundice, Karachi, Pakistan. *GJMS*. 2010; 8(1):12-4.
16. Bhutani VK. Evidence based issues regarding neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *Paediatr Rev*. 2005; 114(1):130-53.
17. Singhal PK, Singh M, Paul VK, Deorari AK, Ghorpade MG. Spectrum of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: An analysis of 454 cases. *Indian Paediatr*. 1992; 29(3):319-25.
18. Bahl L, Sharma R, Sharma J. Aetiology of neonatal jaundice at Shimla. *Indian Paediatr*. 1994; 31(10):1275-8.
19. Merchant RH, Merchant SM, Babar ST. A study of 75 cases of neonatal jaundice. *Indian Paediatr*. 1975; 12(9):889-93.
20. Manorama V, Chatwal J, Singh D. Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, *Indian J Paediatr*. 1988; 55(6):899-904. 21. Bajpai PC, Mishra PK, Agarwal M. An aetiological study of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *Indian J Pediatr*. 1971; 38(286):424-9.
21. Moerschel SK, Cianciaruso LB, Tracy LR. A practical approach to neonatal jaundice. *Am Fam Physician*. 2008; 77(9):1255-62.
22. Khattak ID, Khan TM, Khan P, Shah SMA, Khattak ST, Ali A. Frequency of ABO and rhesus blood groups in district Swat, Pakistan. *J Ayub Med Coll*. 2008; 20(4):127-9.